

EFFECT OF TRANSFORMATIVE ANDRAGOGY EDUCATION ON SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN RIVERS EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, RIVERS

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Keywords:

Transformative, Andragogy, Education, Sustainable, Community Development.

Abstract: *The study investigated the effect of transformative andragogy education on sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial District, Rivers State. The descriptive survey research design was employed to guide the study, which was directed by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study consisted of 10,226 adults of 25 years of age in 8 local government areas on Rivers East senatorial district, Rivers State (6092 in urban and 4134 in rural). A simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 1135 respondents comprising 630 adults from urban and 505 from rural. Data collected was facilitated through a self-structured questionnaire titled "Effect of Transformative Andragogy education on Sustainable Community Development in Rivers East Senatorial District Questionnaire (ETAESCDRESDQ)" was used for data collection. The questionnaires were designed with a 4-point rating scale options ranging from High Extent (HE) = 4 points, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3 Points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 Point respectively, which was deemed adequate for the study. The data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and a t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed adult respondents on critical reflection on sustainable community development to a very high extent and the effect of cultural relevance to a high extent. Based on the findings and conclusion, the researcher recommends the following. The Ministry of Education and Adult Learning centers should organize capacity-building workshops for adult educators on facilitating critical reflection. Rivers East Senatorial District should organize adult education programmers in the eight local government areas to prioritize cultural relevance by designing learning content and activities that reflect learners' cultural values, beliefs, languages, and practices to ensure that andragogy education is meaningful, inclusive, and respectful of learners' identities and experiences.*

INTRODUCTION

Education for transformative Andragogy is the

education that is designed to empower adult to critically reflect on their experiences, challenges

Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

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existing, power structures, and develop new perspectives and skills. Transformative andragogy is targeted at fostering new insights and cogent perspectives. Transformative andragogy is an adult educational approach that focuses on empowering adult individuals to critically reflect on their life experiences and transform their mindsets and perspectives. Nwonkwo and Amadi (2024). Transformative andragogy is an educational process for adults that combines learner-centered facilitation, critical reflection, and culturally rooted dialogue to transform learners' perspectives and empower them to enact positive changes in their lives, organizations, and communities. Transformative andragogy requires facilitators with deep andragogical content knowledge who can create opportunities for critical reflection, dialogue, and empowerment in literacy education, and it involves integrating culturally relevant methods of teaching to foster religious, social, and personal transformation among adult learners. Wordu (2020) stated that education for transformative andragogy should be learner-centered, participatory, and rooted in indigenous knowledge systems, enabling adults to solve community challenges. On this note, transformative andragogy should be a combination of adult learning theory, transformative learning theory, and Freire's critical consciousness theory. UNESCO (2016) Transformative adult education fosters sustainable development by enabling learners to critically understand their worldviews and engage meaningfully in social change efforts.

Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

Andragogy, which originates from the Greek terms Andros meaning ("man") and agogos meaning ("leading"), is a concept propounded by Malcolm Knowles, the American educator, in his 1970 theory on adult learning. Malcolm Knowles defined andragogy as an educational approach that emphasizes the principles. Nwosu and Eze (2023) stated that andragogy is a term used to expand the art and science of helping adult learn, and focusing on their self-directed nature, wealth of life experiences, readiness to learn things relevant to their roles, problem-centered orientation, and intrinsic motivation to achieve personal and professional growth.

Ibe and Mbah. (2023) stated that andragogy has been recognized as a potential catalyst for community development, because andragogy education equips adult citizens with the right knowledge, skills, and attitudes for creative, critical thinking and problem-solving. Transformative andragogy fosters sustainable community development.

Community development is a complex process that requires the active participation and empowerment of community members by focusing on social justice, equity, and participation, and ensuring that all adult members of the community have access to basic needs and opportunities for self-fulfilment, emphasizes on the conservation and efficient use of natural resources, reducing waste and pollution to protect the environment.

A sustainable community is a socially inclusive, economically responsible setting where people's present needs are met without compromising the

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future generations' well-being through active participation, equitable access to resources, and transformative learning interventions.

Okafor (2023). Sustainable development is the process of creating and maintaining communities that balance economic, social, and environmental needs to ensure long-term well-being, equity, and resilience for present and future generations.

On this note, Merrian and Bierema (2023) opined that a sustainable community is a community where adult learning promotes skills development, health awareness, economic productivity, and civic participation, leading to enduring community success. It is where adult education empowers individuals to engage in holistic, productive economic activities, environmental management, and democratic governance for intergenerational benefits.

Brookfield (2023) stress that sustainable communities are those transformed through adult education programmes that reorient values, improve livelihood practices, and build resilience to social and economic setbacks. On this note, a sustainable community enables people to live and work in ways that are environmentally sustainable and enhances quality of life and future generations while protecting and restoring ecological systems. Wangoola and Freire (2023). Adult education serves as the catalyst that empowers communities towards sustainable socio-economic and environmental development. Sustainable community emphasizes transformation through literacy, skills

acquisition, and women's empowerment, which also leads to sustained growth and peaceful coexistence.

Community development is a lifelong-learning process where adult education, group dynamics, and culturally rooted action combine to promote health, literacy, and local governance to achieve sustainable and nationally aligned progress.

Muhammad (2015) opined that community development is both a personal and a top-down model towards self-driven improvement in agriculture, education, and health. This means that community development helps individuals to participate in a culture-sensitive process where rural communities use local structures to reduce illiteracy and build social capital. Uzoaru and Mbah (2020) describe community development as a set of approaches aimed at aligning local actions with national development objectives that drive sustainable social and environmental outcomes. On this note, community development is built through social and group dynamics that foster inclusivity and stewardship.

Critical reflection is purposeful thinking that analyzes experience to generate new understanding and guide improved action.

Fenwich and Tannect (2024) stated that critical reflection in andragogical education is the deliberate process by which adult learners and facilitators evaluate their beliefs, assumptions, and social norms, using dialogue tools and self-awareness to develop deeper understanding, promote perspective transformation, and empower socially responsive action. Onuoha and

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Nwachukwu (2024) stated that critical reflection enables autonomous thinking and frees learners from conditioned assumptions in a professional manner. Adamu and Oladipo (2023) viewed critical reflection as a staged interactive process that enables learners to recognize knowledge relativity and shift their epistemic mindsets. On this note, critical reflection involves the careful questioning of assumptions and societal norms, leading learners towards transformative learning outcomes that promote community development. It guides critical reflection learning by enhancing self-awareness, facilitating a shift in mindsets, and fostering leadership capacities among adult learners as it integrates into education to liberate learners from conditioned assumptions, enabling authentic professional practice. Critical reflection helps adult learners to appreciate the relativity of knowledge by broadening learners' cognitive, epistemological potential. Critical reflection modifies culture and makes it relevant in andragogical education as it integrates learners' cultural background, indigenous knowledge systems, language, and ideologies into teaching and facilitation to enhance engagement, trust, motivation, and learning outcomes. Cercone (2025) stated that integrating local languages, indigenous knowledge systems, and adult philosophies into andragogical practice, and asserting that cultural relevance is a core requirement for effective adult learning. Cultural relevance helps to bridge local realities with transformative learning, and it also helps to

enhance the potential of community development.

Agada and Uzoechina (2023) asserted that culture and background influence adult-facilitator relationships, he suggested that ignoring cultural norms undermines participation and relevance. This shows that indigenous educational practices and storytelling support reflective adult learning. On this note, culturally rooted methods help make meaningful knowledge acquisition in andragogy education.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite, various andragogical educational programmes carried out in communities in Rivers East Senatorial District, sustainable community development remains unachieved as evidenced by youth unemployment, poverty, environmental degradation, and insufficient civic engagement. Traditional approaches to andragogical education in Rivers East often, rely on conventional instructional methods that emphasize rote learning and passive reception of knowledge, rather than fostering critical reflection, cultural relevance, perspective transformation, and empowerment. Transformative andragogy, which integrates adult learning principles with critical reflection, cultural relevance, and action for change, has not been shown to promote empowerment, skills acquisition, participatory problem-solving, and behavioral change among adult learners. However, in Rivers East senatorial District, there appears to be little empirical evidence on the implementation and effect of transformative

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andragogical policies in adult education programmes for sustainable community development outcomes. Furthermore, the researcher observed that many facilitators lack adequate training in transformative andragogical approaches, while curricula remain largely unutilized, the live experiences, indigenous knowledge, and socio-cultural realities of learners, because of this, adult education fail to achieve the intended goals of equipping to an extend individuals with the knowledge, attitudes, and skills necessary to drive sustainable development within their communities. The researcher suggests that the implementation of reflective and cultural relevance could harness and foster transformative andragogical education.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. To what extent does critical reflection enhance effective sustainable community development in the Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State?
2. To what extent does cultural relevance enhance effective sustainable community development in the Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adults aged 25 years on the extent to which critical reflection

enhances sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adults aged 25 years on the extent to which cultural relevance enhances sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study investigated the effect of transformative andragogy on sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial District employed a descriptive research design. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study was 10,226 adults aged 25 years in eight local governments in the Rivers East Senatorial district, consisting of 6092 urban adults and 4134 rural adults respectively. The sample size for this study was 1135 adults, consisting of 630 adults from urban communities and 505 adults from rural communities. This was formulated through Taro Yamane's formula and stratified random sampling techniques. The instrument titled "Effect of Transformative Andragogy education on Sustainable Community Development in Rivers East Senatorial District Questionnaire (ETASCDRESQ)" was used for data collection. The questionnaires were designed with a 4-point rating scale options ranging from High Extent (HE) = 4 points, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3 Points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 Point respectively, which was deemed adequate for the study. The data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to

Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

answer the research questions and a t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Decisions on the research questions were based on the grand mean of the real limit numbers. Items with mean ratings of 0.50-1.49 were rated low extent, those with 1.50-2.49 were rated moderate extent, items with a mean rating of 2.50-3.49 were rated high extent, and those with 3.50-4.00 were rated very high extent. For the

Table 1: Data on the extent to which critical reflection enhances sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	Urban Adult N=506		Rural Adult N=630		Aggregate		RMKS
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	\bar{x}	SD	
1.	Critical reflection improves learning and understanding	4.03	0.56	4.11	0.64	4.07	0.60	VHE
2.	Critical reflection develops problem-solving skills	4.05	0.92	3.96	0.96	4.01	0.94	VHE
3.	Critical reflection enhances teaching, management and leadership practices	4.32	1.22	4.35	1.17	4.34	1.19	VHE
4.	It promotes personal and professional growth	3.14	0.73	3.17	0.72	3.16	0.72	HE
5.	It strengthens confidence And decision-making	4.50	1.02	4.55	0.96	4.53	1.00	VHE
	Grand Mean X/SD	4.01	0.89	4.03	0.89	4.02	0.89	VHE

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The data presented in Table 1 shows the effect of transformative andragogy on sustainable community development in the Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This is evident in the responses of the respondents. The items

hypotheses, if the calculated t-value is equal to or greater than the critical t-value. It will be rejected; otherwise, it will be accepted.

RESULTS

The results are presented in the tables below:
 Research question 1. To what extent does critical reflection enhance sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State?

indicated mean and standard deviation values as follows:

Critical reflection improves learning and understanding (mean = 4.03, 4.11; SD = 0.56, 0.64)

Critical reflection develop problem-solving skills

Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

(Mean 4.05, 3.96; SD = 0.92, 0.96)
 Critical reflection enhances teaching, management, and leadership practices (Mean = 4.32, 4.35, SD = 1.22, 1.17)
 It promotes personal and professional growth (Mean = 3.14, 3.17, SD = 0.73, 0.72)
 Critical reflection strengthens confidence in decision making (Mean = 4.50, 4.55, SD = 1.02, 0.96).

The grand mean and standard deviation of (mean = 4.01, 4.93 SD 0.89, 0.89) respectively. This indicates the effect of critical reflection on sustainable community development to a very

high extent that critical reflection enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Question 2: To what extent does cultural relevance enhance effective sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial District, Rivers State?

Table 2. Data on the extent to which cultural relevance enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	Urban	Adult	Rural Adult	Aggregate	RMKS		
		N=505		N=630				
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	\bar{x}	SD	
6.	Cultural relevance promotes Critical thinking	3.70	0.88	3.75	0.84	3.7	0.86	HE
7.	Cultural relevance improves understanding and learning	4.35	1.16	4.41	1.11	4.38	1.14	VHE
8.	Cultural relevance promotes And equity inclusiveness	3.68	1.61	3.74	1.48	3.71	1.54	HE
9.	It empowers communities With historical and story-Telling knowledge	3.57	0.93	3.63	0.90	3.60	0.92	HE
10.	Cultural relevance preserves cultural heritage	3.72	0.85	3.77	0.82	3.75	0.83	HE
Grand Mean X/SD		3.80	1.17	3.86	1.03	4.56	1.06	VHE

Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The data presented in Table 2 shows the effect of cultural relevance on sustainable community development in the Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This is evident in the mean responses of the respondents. The items indicated the following mean and standard deviation values respectively. Cultural relevance promotes critical thinking (mean = 3.70, 3.75; SD = 0.88, 0.84). It improves understanding and learning (mean = 4.35, 4.41; SD = 1.16, 1.11). It promotes inclusiveness and equity (Mean = 3.68, 3.74; SD = 1.61, 1.48). Cultural relevance empowers communities with historical background and storytelling knowledge (mean 3.57, 3.63; SD = 0.93, 0.90). It preserves cultural heritage (mean = 3.80, 3.86; SD = 1.17, 1.03) respectively. The grand mean and standard deviation indicate that the effect of cultural

relevance on sustainable community development is to a very high extent, that cultural relevance enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adults aged 25 years on the extent to which critical reflection enhances effective, sustainable community development in the River East senatorial district, Rivers state.

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis on the difference between urban and rural adults of 25 years of age response on the extent to which critical reflection enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial district, Rivers state.

Variables NXSD df at-calt-crit Decision

Urban adult of

25 yrs of age 505 4.010.89

11330.050.99±1.96 Accepted;

Rural adult of

25 yrs of age 6304.030.89

Source: fieldsurvey, 2025

Table 3 shows the t-calculated value of 0.99 at 1135 degrees of freedom at a 0.05 level of significance. Since the t-calculated (0.99) is less than the t-critical value (± 1.96), the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adults aged 25 years on the extent to which critical reflection enhances

effective, sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial district, Rivers state.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adults aged 25 years on the extent to which cultural relevance enhances effective, sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial district, Rivers state.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis on the difference between urban and rural adults aged

Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

25 years on the extent to which cultural relevance enhances effective, sustainable community

development in the Rivers East Senatorial district, Rivers state.

Variables NxSDD fat-calt-crit Decisions

Urban adult of 25 yrs of 5053.801.17

11330.050.36+1.96 Accepted

Rural adult of 25 yrs of age 6303.861.03

Source: field survey, 2025

Table 4 shows that the t- Calculated value of 0.36 at 1135 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. Since the t-calculated (0.36) is less than the t-critical value (+1.96), the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adults of 25 years of age on the extent to which cultural relevance enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial.

The result presented in Table 2 shows that there is a very high extent in the mean rating of urban and rural adult education of 25 years of age on sustainable community development in Rivers East Senatorial district, Rivers State. The corresponding hypothesis in Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adult education of 25 years of age on the extent to which andragogy 6.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result in Table 1 shows that critical reflection enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial District, Rivers state to a very high extent. These findings is in agreement with the study of Fenwich and Tannect (2024) they stated that critical reflection enables adult learners to recognize knowledge

relativity and shift their epistemic mindsets. However, the corresponding hypothesis in Table 3, states that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of urban and rural adult of 25 years of age on the extent to which critical reflection enhances effective sustainable community development. In the same vein, the study finds that andragogy plays a crucial role in shaping sustainable community development's critical reflection develop problem solving skills. This also align with the study of Adamu and Oladipo (2023) stated that critical reflection evaluates learner's assumption and social norms, using dialogue tools and self-awareness to develop deeper understanding, promote perspective transformation and empower socially responsive action.

Cultural relevance enhances effective sustainable community development in Rivers East senatorial district, Rivers state. This is in agreement with the study of Cercone (2025), who stated that cultural relevance helps to bridge local realities with transformative learning and enhances the potential of community development. In the same vein, Agada and Uzoechina (2023) stated that cultural relevance

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helps to acquire meaningful knowledge on andragogy education.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that critical reflection and cultural relevance should be integrated fully into andragogy education for transformative adult learning and actualization of sustainable community development in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion, the researcher recommends the following.

1. The ministry of education and adult learning centres should organize capacity building workshops for adult education to facilitate critical reflection.
2. Rivers East Senatorial District should organize adult education programmes in the eight local government areas to prioritize cultural relevance by designing learning content and activities that reflect learners' cultural values, beliefs, languages, and practices to ensure that andragogy is meaningful, inclusive, and respectful of learners' identities and experiences.

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Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD

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Smart Onyemauche Nwonkwo PhD